

Analysis of national and international policy documents related to biodiversity and sustainability

Criteria used to select policy documents for the review

IPBES: To position the *values assessment* within the IPBES domain of discourse, we selected the eight *Summaries-for-Policymakers* that have been approved in IPBES Plenaries to date: Pollinators (2016); Scenarios and Modeling (2016); Regional Assessments (2018) for Africa, the Americas, Asia-Pacific and Europe-Central Asia; Land Degradation and Restoration (2018); and Global (2019).

CBD and NBSAPs: To represent the current discourse associated with the CBD (1992), we reviewed documents associated with the Aichi Targets (CBD 2010, 2013) and the post-2020 Biodiversity Framework (CBD 2020). Plus, we randomly selected 16 National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) from the 169 available at the CBD repository (<https://www.cbd.int/nbsap/about/latest/>). To achieve balanced geopolitical representation, eight NBSAPs were from the Global North and eight from the Global South. Among the selected documents, one was in Spanish and the rest were in English.

Major Global Reports on Biodiversity, Ecosystem Services and Economics: To compare these two biodiversity policy domains with the broader discourse on these topics, during the process of developing the *Values Assessment* several international agreements and reports were identified as relevant. Specifically, to cover the sustainable development interface with the environment, we included two documents related to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainability and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN General Assembly 2015, UN 2020). Plus, to engage sectoral policies regarding agricultural commodities, fisheries/aquaculture, food/agriculture, forestry and gender equity, we incorporated five Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) reports (FAO 2011, 2018a, 2018b, 2018c, 2019). Plus, to assess globally important academic-policy documents related to ecosystem services and economics we selected the MA (synthesis) (2005), The Interim Report of the Dasgupta Review (2020), TEEB (synthesis) (2010), as well as the *Living Planet Report* (2018). Finally, to address a regional perspective, we included the European Union's 2030 Biodiversity Strategy (European Commission, 2020) and the Latin American and Caribbean Escazú Agreement (UN CEPAL, 2018).